

Analysing the Impact of Local Electricity Transactions with EV Penetration on the Electrical Grid

Fernando Lezama, Ricardo Faia, Pedro Faria, and Zita Vale
GECAD, LASI, Polytechnic of Porto
Porto, Portugal
{flz, rfmfa, pnf, zav}@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract—This article analysis, through simulation, the impact that local transactions and the penetration of EVs have on the distribution network and the costs and incomes of local market participants. An auction-based competitive market and mathematical model are provided to simulate end-user transactions with EVs on the low-voltage grid. The proposed framework is validated in a scenario considering 55 end-users (some with PV generation and EVs) and six combined heat and power generators trading energy in the IEEE European Low Voltage Test Feeder system. Furthermore, a distribution system operator is considered by defining network constraints (voltage limits and lines overloading) that ensure the correct operation of the distribution grid.

Index Terms-- Auction-based market, distribution system operator, electric vehicles, local electricity markets, Simulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Local electricity markets (LEM) enable an active role of end-users that can directly transact electricity with peers. LEM also encourages consumers to adopt renewables (e.g., installing PV panels in their homes), reducing carbon emissions and contributing to achieving the environmental goals set by the European Union [1]. In addition, end-users can take advantage of distributed energy resources flexibility (such as the battery of electric vehicles (EVs)) to reduce energy bills and solve grid congestion problems. While such a scenario promises different benefits for market participants, the correct operation of the distribution grid should be guaranteed by the distribution systems operators (DSO), considering the variability and uncertainty of energy flows under these circumstances [2].

Previous works have analyzed different bidding strategies of end-users at the distribution level, even considering network constraints [3], [4]. However, the expected demand that EVs represent, considerably larger compared to other loads in the system, will have an unprecedented impact on the low-voltage grid that is worth exploring. In fact, DSOs need to focus on how to integrate these distributed energy resources efficiently and, at the same time, consider local energy transactions [5], [6].

This article analyzes through simulation the impact of local transactions and EV penetration on the distribution network. A local market framework and mathematical model are provided

to simulate end-user transactions with EVs on the low-voltage grid. The local market is modeled as an auction-based market with different players (namely consumers, prosumers, and small producers) searching for the minimization/maximization of their costs/profits. A metaheuristic, the vortex search (VS) algorithm [7], is used to simulate strategic bidding and find near-optimal solutions to the problem. In addition, different EV types are considered for the end-users evaluating the charging schedule. The proposed framework is validated in a scenario considering 55 end-users and six combined heat and power (CHPs) generators trading energy in the IEEE European Low Voltage Test Feeder system [8]. The framework includes the interaction between end-users and the DSO by defining network constraints (voltage limits, lines overloading, and losses) that ensure the correct operation of the distribution grid and allow electricity transactions between end-users.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The simulation framework considers a LEM in which consumers, prosumers with PV, and CHP producers transact energy to minimize costs and maximize incomes. The innovation of this work is to consider players with EVs and assess the impact that transactions and charging schedules have on the network. Fig. 1 illustrates the LEM.

Figure 1. Participants and interactions in the LEM.

A. Mathematical model

The model is like the one presented in [9], considering a set of consumers $I = \{1, 2, \dots, N_c\}$, and producers $J = \{1, 2, \dots, N_p\}$. The main difference of this work regarding [9] is the consideration of EVs. However, in this work, EVs are mostly loads (only available for charging in periods when the EVs are at home) associated to end-users, and V2G capabilities are not allowed. Also, prosumers equipped with PV can take the role of consumers or producers depending on their surplus of energy. The bi-level optimization model is as follows:

1) *Upper-level (multiple-followers)*: end-users strive to minimize costs (consumers) and maximize incomes (producers) by putting bids and offers into the LEM. The minimization of costs for consumers is modelled as:

$$\min_{s_{i,t}, d_{i,t}} C_i = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_j cp_t \cdot x_{j,i,t} + c_t^{\text{grid}} \cdot E_{i,t}^{\text{buy}} \right) \quad (1a)$$

st.

$$d_{i,t}^{\text{Total}} + E_{i,t}^{\text{EV}+} = \sum_{j \neq i} x_{j,i,t} + E_{i,t}^{\text{buy}} \quad \forall t \in T \quad (1b)$$

$$0 \leq c_t^{\text{F}} \leq cp_t \leq s_{i,t} \leq c_t^{\text{grid}} \quad \forall t \in T \quad (1c)$$

where the tuple $(s_{i,t}, d_{i,t})$ includes the consumer price bid $s_{i,t}$ for the amount of energy $d_{i,t}$ at time t . $x_{j,i,t}$ is the energy bought in the LEM by agent i from agent j LEM (kWh); $E_{i,t}^{\text{buy}}$ is the energy bought from the grid by agent i (kWh); cp_t is the LEM clearing price (EUR/kWh); and c_t^{grid} is the grid or retailer tariff (EUR/kWh). Constraint (1b) guarantees a supply of the total demand $d_{i,t}^{\text{Total}} + E_{i,t}^{\text{EV}+}$ either by the LEM or the grid; constraint (1c) sets the LEM clearing price cp_t between feed-in tariff c_t^{F} and the bid price $s_{i,t}$ and grid tariff c_t^{grid} . The variables are all non-negative values.

Producers, on the other hand, search for the maximization of incomes as:

$$\max_{s_{j,t}, g_{j,t}} In_j = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_i cp_t \cdot x_{j,i,t} + c_t^{\text{F}} \cdot E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}} - C_{j,t}^{\text{total}} \right) \quad (2a)$$

st.

$$g_{i,j}^{\text{PV}} - d_{i,t}^{\text{Total}} - \sum_v E_{i,t}^{\text{EV}-} = \sum_{i,j \neq i} x_{j,i,t} + E_{j,t}^{\text{sell}} \text{ for PV } \forall t \in T \quad (2b)$$

$$g_{j,t}^{\text{CHP}} = \sum_{i,j \neq i} x_{j,i,t} \text{ for CHP } \forall t \in T \quad (2c)$$

$$0 \leq c_t^{\text{F}} \leq s_{j,t} \leq cp_t \leq c_t^{\text{grid}} \quad \forall t \in T \quad (2d)$$

where the tuple $(s_{j,t}, g_{j,t})$ includes the price offer $s_{j,t}$ for the amount of energy $g_{j,t}$ at time t . $x_{j,i,t}$ is the energy sold by agent j to agent i in the LEM (kWh); $E_{j,t}^{\text{sell}}$ is the energy sold (kWh) to the grid by agent j (we assume that only PV generation can be injected into the grid); cp_t is the LEM clearing price (EUR/kWh); c_t^{F} is the feed-in tariff paid only to PV generation (EUR/kWh); and $C_{j,t}^{\text{total}}$ is production cost of local generation. Such cost $C_{j,t}^{\text{total}}$ is assumed to be 0 for PV generation and $2 \cdot b_{\text{CHP}} \cdot \sqrt{G_{j,t}}$ for the CHPs, with b_{CHP} as a cost factor, and $G_{j,t}$ as

the produced energy. Constraint (2b) guarantees that the surplus from PV generation is injected into the grid and offered in the LEM; constraint (2c) states that CHP generation is offered into the LEM only; and constraint (2d) is used to establish the price offer $s_{j,t}$ less or equal the clearing price cp_t , and between the feed-in tariff c_t^{F} and the grid tariff c_t^{grid} .

Finally, the charging scheduling of the EVs is modelled as:

$$E_{i,j,t}^{\text{EV}+} \cdot \mathbf{X}_{i,j,t}^{\text{EV}+} \leq \alpha \quad \forall t \in T \quad (3a)$$

$$SoC_{i,j,t}^{\text{min}} \leq SoC_{i,j,t} \leq SoC_{i,j,t}^{\text{max}} \quad (3b)$$

$$SoC_{i,j,t} = SoC_{(i,j,t-1)} + \eta_{i,j}^+ \cdot E_{i,j,t}^{\text{EV}+} \quad (3c)$$

$$SoC_{i,j,t_0} \leq SoC_{i,j,T} \quad (3d)$$

where (3a) limits the amount of energy to charge up to the charging rate α at each period t ; binary variables $\mathbf{X}_{i,j,t}^{\text{EV}+}$ is used to indicate when the EV is connected and able to charge (equals to 0 when the EV is on trip); (3b) limits the battery state of charge to the minimum preference level $SoC_{i,j,t}^{\text{min}}$ and maximum battery capacity level $SoC_{i,j,t}^{\text{max}}$; (3c) models the state of charge of the battery considering the charging values and battery efficiency; and finally, (3d) states that the final state of charge should be greater or equal to the initial state of charge (this is used to guarantee that the EVs charge the energy they spend during day trips).

2) *Lower-level (single-follower)*: costs and incomes of market participants depend on the clearing price obtained in the LEM. Thus, the LEM is modeled as a symmetric pool-based market. First, supply and demand curves are obtained by creating the sets GE (ordering the offers of energy $(s_{j,t}, g_{j,t})$ from lowest to highest price) and DE (ordering the bids for energy $(s_{i,t}, d_{i,t})$ from highest to lowest price). With those sets, a linear problem is formulated as [10]:

$$\max_{d_i^*, g_j^*} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \lambda_i^d \cdot d_i^* - \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \lambda_j^g \cdot g_j^* \quad (4a)$$

st.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_c} d_i^* - \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} g_j^* = 0 \quad : cp_t \text{ (dual variable)} \quad (4b)$$

$$0 \leq d_i^* \leq DE_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_c \quad (4c)$$

$$0 \leq g_j^* \leq GE_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_p \quad (4d)$$

where d_i^* and g_j^* are the demand bids and supply offers ordered by price (i.e., belonging to sets DE_i and GE_j), and λ_i^d and λ_j^g are their corresponding bid/offer prices. Thus, Eq. (4a) maximizes the social welfare of market participants; Eq. (4b) is the balance constraint, and its dual variable is the clearing price cp_t ; Equations (4c) and (4d) guarantee the generation and consumption limits. After solving this linear problem, a reverse procedure is used to determine the LEM transactions $x_{i,j}$ and $x_{j,i}$ from the accepted bids/offers d_i^* and g_j^* .

B. DSO Network Constraints

The transacted energy in the LEM occurs at the low voltage level impacting the distribution network. To assess such impact,

we implement a power flow validation in MATPOWER after clearing the LEM. The DSO's minimization of voltage violations and losses is modelled as:

$$\min_{g_j^{\text{CHP}}} DN^{\text{impact}} = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_{b \in \Omega_b} B_{t,b} + \sum_{b \in \Omega_b} \theta_{t,b} + \sum_{l \in \Omega_l} L_{t,l} + \sum_{l \in \Omega_l} P_{t,l}^{\text{loss}} + \sum_{l \in \Omega_l} Q_{t,l}^{\text{loss}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where DN^{impact} is the impact in the network measured in function of the CHP generation g_j^{CHP} , and the response of the power flow with the voltage/angle/line limit violations ($B_{t,b} / \theta_{t,b} / L_{t,l}$) set to 1 if a voltage/angle/line violation occur in bus b or line l (0 otherwise); and the active and reactive power losses $P_{t,l}^{\text{loss}}$ and $Q_{t,l}^{\text{loss}}$ in line l (kW). It is worth to notice that DN^{impact} is used as a unitless value to represent the status of the network simple and easy to implement, but do not reflect realistically how the DSO would validate the status of the network [9] (something that is out of the scope of this research).

III. SIMULATION AND VALIDATION FRAMEWORK

As it was done in [9], the simulation framework uses the VS algorithm to improve the solutions iteratively. We use that mechanism to simulate a competitive market in which players search for the best bidding strategy to maximize profits. A set of players $K = \{1, 2, \dots, N_k\}$ is defined with k being either a consumer or producer. A player defines a tuple $(q_{k,t}, p_{k,t}, [EV_{k,t}]) \forall k \in K, \forall t \in T$ containing bids/offers of energy and price and the energy to charge the EV. Thus, a solution is a vector $\vec{x} = \{[q_{k,t}] \cup [p_{k,t}] \cup [EV_{k,t}]\}$ including the bids/offers of energy and price, and energy to charge the EVs for each agent k . A sign convention is used in the variables of quantity ($q_{k,t}$), with a positive value representing agents that buy energy and a negative value for agents that offer energy into the market. The bounds of variables are defined as $[0, d_{i,t}^{\text{Total}}]$ (i.e., between 0 and the maximum consumption) for bids of consumers, and $[g_{j,t}^{\text{max}}, 0]$ (i.e., between 0 and their maximum production/surplus capacity) for producers and prosumers (i.e., group of variables $[q_{k,t}]$); $[c_t^F, c_t^{\text{grid}}] \forall t \in T$ for the bounds of prices (i.e., group of variables $[p_{k,t}]$) with prices between the feed-in tariff and the grid tariff; and $[0, \alpha]$ for the EV charging variables (i.e., group of variables $[EV_{k,t}]$). Details of solution encoding for metaheuristics can be found in [11] and are omitted due to space constraints.

Other assumptions in the implementation are: each prosumer with PV surplus is forced to offer that energy into the LEM, and only after, inject it into the grid; CHP offer price $s_{j,t}$ is adjusted to be higher or equal to the production cost $g_{j,t}$ (to avoid generation costs); also, since CHPs have a low generation volume, it is not allowed to sell the energy directly to the retailer or the wholesale market; consumers are assumed to be price takers (i.e., $s_{i,t} = c_t^{\text{grid}}$) and inelastic loads ($d_{i,t} = d_{i,t}^{\text{Total}}$); thus, the focus on the improvement of solutions is done only on the production side.

After a solution is constructed, the lower-level problem is solved according to the LP model from Eq. (4). The results

from this step are the accepted bids/offers $x_{i,j,t} / x_{j,i,t}$ and clearing price cp_t . With this information, the costs and income for each player can be calculated using Eqs. (1a) and (2a) and stored in a vector as:

$$U_{k,t} = \begin{cases} -C_{i,t} & \text{if } k \text{ is a consumer agent} \\ P_{j,t} & \text{if } k \text{ is a generator agent} \end{cases} \quad (6a)$$

$$U_k^{\text{total}} = \sum_{t=1}^T U_{k,t} \quad (6b)$$

where $C_{i,t}$ and $P_{j,t}$ are the objectives of each player optimized in the iterative process. The profits are recorded in a vector $A_{\text{profit}} = [U_1^{\text{total}}, \dots, U_k^{\text{total}}, \dots, U_{N_k}^{\text{total}}]$. Before calculating the fitness, and after the calculation of the LEM response, the power flow is run to determine the network status and calculate penalties in function of the losses and violations. A penalty function $p_t^{\text{DN}} = w \cdot DN^{\text{impact}}$ is defined and combined with the LEM results (Eq. (6)) in the fitness function to reflect the performance of a solution:

$$\text{Fit}(\vec{x}) = -\text{mean}(A_{\text{profit}}) + \text{std}(A_{\text{profit}}) + \sum_{t=1}^T p_t^{\text{LEM}} + \sum_{t=1}^T p_t^{\text{DN}} \quad (7)$$

where $A_{\text{profit}} = [U_1, \dots, U_k, \dots, U_{N_k}]$ are the profits of players; **mean()** and **std()** return the mean and standard deviation values of such profits; $\sum_{t=1}^T p_t^{\text{LEM}}$ is a penalty added to the fitness when the LEM is not cleared ($1e4$ in this work); and $\sum_{t=1}^T p_t^{\text{DN}}$ is the penalty related to network constraints. The fitness function provides a sense of profit maximization, LEM performance, and network validation, which are the indicators we are interested in finding in this work.

IV. CASE STUDY

To test the proposed model, we consider a local energy community with 12 consumers, 42 prosumers with PV generation, and 6 CHP generators, having a total of 61 different players. Also, we assume that 29 prosumers have EVs.

Figure 2. Accumulated load and generation.

Figure 2 presents the LEC consumption and generation. Notice that we artificially created an abnormal peak consumption during periods 18 to 20, creating some congestion

problems in the network. We assume that this peak is caused by a special event (e.g., a sporting event) in the community area. On the other hand, the generation peak is registered at period 14 with 140.74 kWh. The CHP generators have a maximum capacity of 10kW with a factor $b_{CHP} = 0.20$ EUR/kWh used to calculate their production.

Regarding pricing, we consider two tariffs in the experiments, a flat tariff with 0.158 €/kWh for all periods, and a double tariff with 0.1023 €/kWh in off-peak periods (23h to 7h), and 0.1924 €/kWh in peak periods (8h to 22h). Also, it is assumed a constant feed-in tariff [12] of $c_t^f = 0.045 \forall t \in T$.

Regarding EVs, Table I presents the six different EVs models considered in our experiments. The departure and arrival periods for the EVs are generated according to two types of routines. Specifically, in our case study 20 EVs execute the day routine (morning departure and afternoon arrival), 6 EVs the night routine (afternoon departure and morning arrival), and 3 EVs are parked at home during all periods. We also assume that EVs have no V2G capabilities (i.e., they are not allowed to discharge the EV batteries for energy arbitrage)

TABLE I. EVS MODELS AND CHARACTERISTICS

Brand	Model	N ^o	Cons. (Wh/km)	Bat. Cap. (kWh)	Min. SoC (kWh)
Nissan	Leaf	5	180	62	12.4
Honda	e	4	180	28.5	5.7
Tesla	Model X	6	226	100	20
Porsche	Tacan 4S	5	215	93	18.6
Mercedes	Eqs 580	5	183	107.8	21.56
Jaguar	i-Pace	4	220	90	18

Regarding the distribution network, Figure 3 presents the single line diagram of modified IEEE European LV test feeder used in this study [8].

Figure 3. Equivalent model of the modified IEEE low voltage test feeder, adapted from [8].

The radial network is connected to a medium voltage transformer of 0.8 MVA. We modified the original network by replacing the line between bus 15 to bus 28 (28 m) with a line between bus 1 to bus 28 (106 m), and the line between bus 58 to bus 68 (3 m) with a line between bus 1 to bus 68 (159 m). The load buses with PV generators installed can use the

generation for self-consumption or sell the excess to the grid or the LEM. Finally, 6 CHP units are included in buses 18, 27, 28, 70, 79, and 108.

Finally, Table II presents the different scenarios used to evaluate the proposed methodology. The worst-case scenario assumes that there are no local transactions and that the EVs are connected and charging in the homes. The business-as-usual (BAU) scenario does not allow local transactions but considers smart charging scheduling of EVs. Case 1 is defined to study the impact of the optimization model when the LEM with intelligent management of EVs battery charge is considered. The three scenarios are simulated with both tariffs also to analyze the impact of pricing on the decisions and the distribution network.

TABLE II. ANALYSED SCENARIOS IN THIS ARTICLE.

Scenario	Tariff	LEM	EV-EMS
Worst-case	Flat	No	No
	Double	No	No
BAU	Flat	No	Yes
	Double	No	Yes
Case 1	Flat	Yes	Yes
	Double	Yes	Yes

To deal with the stochastic nature of the optimizer we performed 10 runs for each experiment, reporting the best values of different metrics. The experiments were implemented in MATLAB 2018a in a computer with Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-8650U CPU@1.90GHz processor with 16GB of RAM running Windows 10. For VS, the number of iterations has been set to 2000 and the number of neighbor solutions to 20 as in [9].

V. CASE STUDY

The overall costs, incomes, and profits for the main type of agents and each considered scenario are shown in Table III. The table also includes the fitness value and execution time of the worst-case and BAU scenarios, and the best solution found over ten runs with the VS algorithm in Case 1. The first thing to notice is the need for more income for prosumers and producers in the worst- and BAU scenarios. This occurs since local transactions cannot happen without the LEM. Comparing the flat and double tariffs in the three scenarios, the costs for consumers and prosumers decrease in the worst- and BAU scenarios (although very slightly). However, with the LEM (Case 1), the costs of consumer/prosumer increase with the double tariff. Even when Case 1 reports the lower costs compared to worst- and BAU scenarios, the effect of the double tariff is different, apparently affecting the overall profits of the participants w.r.t. to the flat tariff. We should consider two things that might be causing this counterintuitive effect. The first is related to the solution method, the VS algorithm. Being a metaheuristic implies that the solution found is sub-optimal; thus, it is possible that a better solution can be found with a more effective algorithm or a different set of parameters (which is out of the scope of this research). The second point is related to the CHP generation cost. With the low-price rate of the double tariff in periods 1 to 8, 23 and 24, CHPs have no incentive to participate in the LEM. In addition, in the periods of high-price rate (i.e., from period 9 to period 22), the LEM might result in higher prices for the community since the upper bound tariff increases for those periods compared to the flat

TABLE III. OVERALL COSTS/INCOMES/PROFITS, FITNESS, AND EXECUTION TIME IN EACH SCENARIO.

Scenario	Tariff	Consumers & prosumers (EUR)			Producers (EUR)			Total (EUR)			Fitness	Time (mins)
		Cost	Income	Profit (loss ^a)	Cost	Income	Profit (loss ^a)	Cost	Income	Profit (loss ^a)		
Worst-case	Flat	885.10	0.00	-885.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	885.10	0.00	-885.10	24630.75	-
	Double	827.82	0.00	-827.82	0.00	0.00	0.00	827.82	0.00	-827.82	24628.91	-
BAU	Flat	413.87	0.00	-413.87	0.00	0.00	0.00	413.87	0.00	-413.87	12214.12	25.11
	Double	412.11	0.00	-412.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	412.11	0.00	-412.11	10813.97	25.05
Case 1	Flat	366.94	15.93	-351.01	50.65	55.38	4.74	366.94	20.67	-346.27	11.47	36.79
	Double	401.98	28.85	-373.14	45.92	55.14	9.23	401.98	38.07	-363.91	13.08	42.77

^a Profits are calculated as Incomes minus Costs. Thus, a negative value of profits indicates a loss (i.e., costs are higher than incomes).

tariff. To corroborate this point, Fig. 4 shows the tariffs and obtained clearing prices in the LEM in the two cases. As we can see, the LEM prices in the high-rate part of the double prices are much higher than those obtained with the flat tariff.

Another aspect worth analyzing is related to the impact of EVs management and LEM on the network constraints and voltage losses. Table IV Presents the line, bus, and angle number of violations and voltage losses for all the analyzed scenarios to assess that. It can be confirmed that the worst-case scenario presents many line and bus violations due to the large load that EVs represent being always plugged and charging. With the EV charging management, the line violations are eliminated, and both bus violations and losses are significantly reduced (although not eliminated). Finally, the bus violations are eliminated with the consideration of the LEM, mostly due to the participation of CHPs with the local generation. Also, notice that the network losses slightly increase when the double tariff is considered, an effect related to the low-price rate in early periods and the impossibility of CHP generation in those periods.

TABLE IV. DN CONSTRAINTS RESULTS OBTAINED IN EACH CASE.

Scenario	Tariff	Limit violations (number)			Losses (kW)	
		Line	Bus	Angle	Active	Reactive
Worst-case	Flat	4	242	0	325.05	52.89
	Double	4	242	0	325.05	52.89
BAU	Flat	0	122	0	106.23	17.29
	Double	0	108	0	106.03	17.28
Case 1	Flat	0	0	0	58.23	9.45
	Double	0	0	0	66.94	10.87

Finally, Fig. 5 shows the energy bought and sold from the grid and the LEM (with the PV and CHP generation in the back)

for Case 1 with both tariffs. These plots are used to confirm that CHPs do not produce energy in low-price rates (1-8, 23-24) of the double tariff (see Fig. 5b), and also these graphs clearly show the periods of high demand (periods 18, 19, and 20) that results in network constraint violations, a problem solved with the LEM and the EV energy management.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This article analyzes the impact that EVs and the LEM have on the low-voltage grid. Three scenarios have been considered to this end: one (worst-case scenario) in which there is no LEM and the EVs are always plugged in and charging the battery; second in which smart charging of EVs is considered (BAU scenario); and finally, a scenario in which the LEM and smart charging is considered. In addition, two different tariff schemes have been studied in each of the scenarios mentioned, a flat tariff and a double tariff. Results show that, as expected, smart charging and considering local transactions reduce end-user costs and help alleviate network issues and reduce voltage losses. In addition, contrary to what was expected, the double tariff negatively impacts consumers' costs when the LEM is considered (Case 1 scenario). This occurs due to the limited participation of CHPs in low-price rate periods (i.e., CHPs cannot compete with the offered grid tariff) and an increase in the LEM clearing price in high-price rate periods. Such results make evident the need for a deeper analysis of EVs and local market structures' impact on the network operation. Thus, avenues for future research include considering DSO and LEM participants' coordination and studying how different objectives from different participants interact in such structures. Also, considering more advanced technologies and management strategies on the EVs side (e.g., V2G capabilities) would certainly play a major role in the LEM and market results. Finally, the fairness aspects related to pricing mechanisms and profits in LEMs where end-users have different characteristics is another interesting research avenue.

Figure 4. Clearing prices for: (a) Case 1 – flat tariff; (b) Case 1 – double tariff.

Figure 5. Transacted energy in the LEM and grid, and PV and CHP generation for: (a) Case 1 – flat tariff; (b) Case 1 – double tariff.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Lezama, J. Soares, P. Hernandez-Leal, M. Kaisers, T. Pinto, and Z. Vale, "Local Energy Markets: Paving the Path Toward Fully Transactive Energy Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 4081–4088, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2833959.
- [2] K. Sevdari, L. Calcaro, P. B. Andersen, and M. Marinelli, "Ancillary services and electric vehicles: An overview from charging clusters and chargers technology perspectives," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 167, p. 112666, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112666.
- [3] A. Papalexopoulos, R. Frowd, and A. Birbas, "On the development of organized nodal local energy markets and a framework for the TSO-DSO coordination," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 189, p. 106810, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.epr.2020.106810.
- [4] G. Tsaousoglou, J. S. Giraldo, P. Pinson, and N. G. Paterakis, "Mechanism Design for Fair and Efficient DSO Flexibility Markets," *IEEE Trans Smart Grid*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 2249–2260, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2020.3048738.
- [5] N. B. Arias, S. Hashemi, P. B. Andersen, C. Treholt, and R. Romero, "Distribution System Services Provided by Electric Vehicles: Recent Status, Challenges, and Future Prospects," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 1–20, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TITS.2018.2889439.
- [6] A. K. Kalakanti and S. Rao, "Computational Challenges and Approaches for Electric Vehicles," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1145/3582076.
- [7] B. Dogan and T. Omez, "A new metaheuristic for numerical function optimization: Vortex Search algorithm," *Inf Sci (N Y)*, vol. 293, pp. 125–145, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2014.08.053.
- [8] M. A. Khan and H. Barry, "A Reduced Electrically-Equivalent Model of the IEEE European Low Voltage Test Feeder.," 2021, doi: 10.36227/tehrxiv.16785832.v1.
- [9] F. Lezama, R. Faia, and Z. Vale, "Bidding in Local Electricity Markets Considering Low Voltage Grid Constraints," in *2022 18th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*, IEEE, Sep. 2022, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/EEM54602.2022.9921122.
- [10] E. M. Mengelkamp, "Engineering Local Electricity Markets for Residential Communities," Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie (KIT), 2019.
- [11] F. Lezama et al., "Bidding in local electricity markets with cascading wholesale market integration," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 131, p. 107045, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107045.
- [12] Republica Portuguesa, *Portaria n.º 80/2020, de 25 de março*. Lisbon: Diário da República n.º 60/2020, Série I de 2020-03-25, 2020, pp. 5–7.